

Technology exposure during Covid-19 Pandemic and its Impact on Psychological and Social Health of Students: Moderating Role of Technostress

Soroya, Saira Hanif

Minhaj University Lahore, Pakistan |
sairasroya@gmail.com

Akhter, Shamim

Minhaj University Lahore, Pakistan |
shamfgcollege@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The outbreak of COVID-19 coronavirus disease has rapidly progressed around the world and became a pandemic within a short period. It has affected almost all walks of life including social, economic and education sector of society. Education mode has been changed and transferred from face-to-face education to online learning during COVID-19. Furthermore, social distancing has also pushed youngsters to use technology more frequently for leisure time and social interaction. While using technology students' inability to adjust with communication techniques, the problem of connecting devices and a variety of computer applications creates technostress among the students and it affects students' psychological, mental, social, and physical health. The study is designed to identify the impact of techno exposure on the social and psychological health of students and to examine the mediating role of technostress between technology exposure and psychological and social health of students. The population of the study comprised of undergraduate students (social sciences) from two Higher Education Commission recognized universities of Lahore. A convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data from students through online questionnaires. The current study presents results of initial data which is 100. Structural equation model (SEM) is used to test the proposed model by using ADANCO (2.1). The results exhibited that compulsory e-learning significantly affect the social health of students, they remain more isolated and detached with the society, however it is not a reason of technostress and psychological disturbance. In addition, social interaction through technology develops technostress that results into psychological challenges and ultimately ends up with social isolation. It is interesting to note that use of technology for leisure and self-learning has no negative consequences in terms of psychological and social health. Technostress proved a significant mediator between technology use and psychological and social health. The less technostress will result less unhealthy psychological and social state, and less use of technology for social interaction will develop less technostress among students. The results can be helpful to guide youngsters to manage technology use and technostress so that their psychological and social health may be ensured.

KEYWORDS

COVID-19; Technostress; Psychological health; Social health; SEM; ADANCO